

Utility of 2-amino-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-chromene-3-carbonitriles in synthesis of chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine and chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidine derivatives of pharmaceutical interest

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Chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (5, 6 and 8) have been prepared by the reaction of 2-amino-7,7-dimethyl-4-substitutedphenyl-5-oxo-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-chromene-3-carbonitriles (2a,b) with formic acid, formamide and phenyl isothiocyanate respectively. The reaction of 3-amino-4-iminochromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (11) with formic acid, acetic anhydride and *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde have furnished the chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidines (12, 14 and 15) respectively.

Selected substituted chromenes¹ as well as different pyrimidine ring containing heterocycles² possess various biological activities. We report here the synthesis of 2-aminochromeno-3-carbonitrile and its conversion to chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines and chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidines to evaluate their biological activity.

Thus, compounds 2a-c were prepared through one-pot reaction of 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (1), aromatic aldehydes and malononitrile in ethanolic piperidine. On using ammonium acetate as catalyst instead of piperidine, the same products (2a-c) were obtained in good yields. Compounds 2a-c were also obtained from the bicomponent condensation of 1 with α -cyanocinnamionitriles under the same conditions³.

The enamionitriles (2a-c) proved to be a versatile material and its chemical behaviour towards different reagents was studied. Thus, 2a reacted with acetic anhydride, for which two products 3 and 4 seemed possible. Structure 3 was ruled out due to the presence of C \equiv N band in the ir spectra. Treatment of 2a with formic acid yielded the corresponding 8,8-dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,5,6,7,9-pentahydro-4,6-dioxo-8H-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (5). Refluxing 2a,b in formamide afforded 4-amino-8,8-dimethyl-5-substituted-phenyl-5,6,7,9-tetrahydro-6-oxo-8H-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (6a,b). In addition, the behaviour of 2 towards phenyl isothiocyanate under different conditions was also studied. Thus, reaction of 2a with phenyl isothiocyanate in boiling ethanol afforded a product

(C₂₅H₂₂N₃O₂SCl) for which two structures 7 and 8a seemed possible. Structure 7 was established for the reaction product on the basis of its ir spectrum. Compounds 2a,b were also reacted with phenyl isothiocyanate in pyridine or DMF to give 4-amino-8,8-dimethyl-5-substitutedphenyl-3-phenyl-2,3,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-6-oxo-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2-thiones (8a,b). Compound (8a) was also obtained by heating 7 in pyridine (Scheme 1).

The enamionitriles (2a,b) were reacted with triethylorthoformate in acetic anhydride to yield the ethoxymethylideneamino derivatives (9a,b). Aminolysis of the latter in ethanol at room temperature afforded (6a,b), (m.p. and m.m.p.). Reaction of 9a with benzylamine and butylamine in ethanol at room temperature effected cyclization to give 4-imino-8,8-dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(benzyl or *n*-butyl)-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-8H-6-oxochromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (10a,b). The reaction of 9a with an equivalent of hydrazine hydrate for short time gave the chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (11). Interaction of 11 with triethylorthoformate or formic acid afforded 9,9-dimethyl-12-(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-11-one (12). Condensation of 11 with acetic anhydride afforded chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (13). On repeating the same reaction for long time period yielded 2,9,9-trimethyl-12-(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-11-one (14). Condensation of 11 with *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde furnished 9,9-dimethyl-2,12-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-

Scheme 1

chromeno[3,2-*e*][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-*c*]pyrimidin-11-one (15). Its structure was confirmed by analytical and spectral data and through its synthesis by condensation of 11 with *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride (Scheme 2)

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected Ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Jasco FT/IR 5300 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Jeol FX100 spectrometer (200 MHz) using TMS as internal reference (Chemical shifts in δ ppm) and mass spectra on a EI + Q1MS LMR UPLR instrument. Microanalytical data were obtained from the Microanalytical Data Unit at Cairo University.

Compound 2a was prepared according to the reported method³

2-Amino-7,7-dimethyl-4-substituted-phenyl-5-oxo-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-chromene-3-carbonitriles (2b,c) : **Method (A)** · A suspension of equimolar (0.01 mol) amounts of the appropriate aromatic aldehyde, malononitrile and 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (1) in ethanol (40 ml) and piperidine (1 ml) or ammonium acetate (0.02 mol) was re-

fluxed for 1–2 h. After completion of the reaction (tlc control) the mixture was cooled and the resulting solid was crystallized from proper solvent ; 2b (ethanol), (80%), m.p. 179° (Found . C, 65.80; H, 6.50; N, 7.10. C₂₁H₂₄N₂O₅ requires : C, 65.62; H, 6.25; N, 7.29%), ν_{\max} 3400, 3261 (NH₂), 2900 (CH-aliph), 2174 (C≡N), 1670 cm⁻¹ (C=O, δ 1.07 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.12 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.25 (2H, s, CH₂), 2.45 (2H, s, CH₂), 3.79 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.82 (6H, s, 2 × OCH₃), 4.33 (1H, s, 4H-pyran³), 4.56 (2H, s, NH₂, cancelled with D₂O) and 6.42 (2H, s, ArH); 2c (ethanol) (95%), m p. 250° (Found . C, 66.90; H, 5.50; N, 8.60. C₁₉H₂₀N₂O₄ requires : C, 67.05; H, 5.88; N, 8.23%), ν_{\max} 3450 (OH), 3300, 3230 (NH₂), 2174 (C≡N), 1675 cm⁻¹ (C=O). **Method (B)** : A mixture of α -cyanocinnamitriles (0.01 mol), 5,5-dimethylcyclohexane-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) and catalytic amount of piperidine (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 2h. The resulting solid was crystallized from proper solvent to give 2b,c

2-Acetamido-7,7-dimethyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-oxo-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-chromene-3-carbonitrile (4) : A solution of 2a (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was

Scheme 2

refluxed for 2 h. After cooling the solid obtained was crystallized from benzene, (65%), m.p. 250° (Found : C, 64.60; H, 5.40; N, 7.20. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 64.77; H, 5.12; N 7.55%); ν_{max} 3200 (NH), 2960 (CH-aliph), 2221 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1740, 1674 cm^{-1} (C=O).

8,8-Dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,5,6,7,9-pentahydro-4,6-dioxo-8H-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (5) : A solution of 2a (0.01 mol) in formic acid (5 ml), was refluxed for 1 h. The solid obtained was crystallized from ethanol, (60%), m.p. 160° (Found : C, 63.60; H, 4.90; N, 7.70. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 63.95; H, 4.76; N, 7.85%); ν_{max} 3134 (NH), 1757, 1654 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.2 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.1 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.3 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.4 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 7.4 (4H, AB-system), 8.3 (1H, s, pyrimidine-H), 9.5 (1H, s, NH, cancelled D_2O).

4-Amino-8,8-dimethyl-5-substituted-phenyl-5,6,7,9-tetrahydro-6-oxo-8H-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (6a,b) : A solution of 2a,b (0.01 mol) in formamide (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The solid obtained was crystallized from proper solvent : 6a (benzene) (70%), m.p. 170° (Found : C, 64.50; H, 5.30; N, 11.60. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ requires : C, 64.13; H, 5.06; N, 11.81%), ν_{max} 3380, 3200 (NH₂), 1675 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ 0.9 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.1 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.0 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.2 (2H, s, CH_2), 4.3 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 5.4 (2H,

s, NH₂, cancelled by D_2O), 7.6 (4H, AB-system), 8.5 (1H, s, pyrimidine-H); 6b (benzene) (72%), m.p. 195° (Found : C, 64.10; H, 6.30; N, 10.50. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5$ requires : C, 64.23; H, 6.08; N, 10.21%), ν_{max} 3400, 3200 (NH₂), 1665 cm^{-1} (C=O).

1-[3-Cyano-7,7-dimethyl-4-(4-chlorophenyl)-5-oxo-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-chromen-2-yl]-3-phenylthiourea (7) : A mixture of 2a (0.01 mol), phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The solid obtained was crystallized from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 110° (Found : C, 64.90; H, 4.40; N, 9.30. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$ requires : C, 64.72; H, 4.74; N, 9.06%); ν_{max} 3207, 3184 (NH), 2189 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$), 1665 cm^{-1} (C=O).

4-Amino-8,8-dimethyl-5-substituted-phenyl-3-phenyl-2,3,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-6-oxo-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidin-2-thione (8a,b). **Method (C)** : A mixture of 2a,b (0.01 mol), phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) and pyridine (20 ml) was refluxed in an oil bath for 5–6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with ethanol and the resulting solid was crystallized from proper solvent : 8a (DMF/EtOH) (90%), m.p. > 330° (Found : C, 64.50, H, 4.90; N, 9.20. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{SCl}$ requires : C, 64.72; H, 4.74; N, 9.06%), ν_{max} 3417, 3200 (NH₂), 1658 cm^{-1} (C=O), δ 0.89 (3H, s, CH_3), 1.04 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.26 (2H, s, CH_2), 2.56 (2H, s,

CH₂), 4.7 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 5.26 (2H, s, NH₂, cancelled with D₂O), 7.27–7.8 (4H, m, ArH); **8b** (ethanol) (72%), m.p. 210° (Found : C, 64.40; H, 5.30; N, 8.30). C₂₈H₂₉N₃O₅S requires : C, 64.73; H, 5.58; N, 8.09%, ν_{\max} 3380, 3210 (NH₂), 1680 cm⁻¹ (C=O). *Method (D)* : A solution of **7** (0.01 mol) in pyridine (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and diluted with ethanol/H₂O to give **8a** : *m/z* 463 (100%), 464 (42%).

2-Ethoxymethylideneamino-7,7-dimethyl-4-substituted-phenyl-4,5,6,8-tetrahydro-7H-5-oxo-chromene-3-carbonitriles (9a,b) : A mixture of **2a,b** (0.01 mol), triethyl orthoformate (2 ml) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) was refluxed for 8 h. The reaction mixture was left to cool overnight and the solid formed was crystallized from proper solvent : **9a** (AcOH) (85%), m.p. 170° (Found : C, 65.80; H, 5.20; N, 7.60). C₂₁H₂₁N₂O₃Cl requires : C, 65.53; H, 5.46; N, 7.28%, ν_{\max} 3020 (CH-arom), 2962 (CH-aliph), 2208 (C≡N), 1664 cm⁻¹ (C=O), δ 1.00 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 1.34 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.1 (2H, d, CH₂), 2.52 (2H, s, CH₂), 4.3 (2H, q, OCH₂), 4.37 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 7.27 (4H, AB-system), 8.58 (1H, s, N=CH-); **9b** (ethanol) (70%), m.p. 130° (Found : C, 65.10; H, 6.60; N, 6.70). C₂₄H₂₈N₂O₆ requires : C, 65.80; H, 5.20; N, 7.60%.

4-Imino-8,8-dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(benzyl or n-butyl)-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-8H-6-oxo-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (10a,b) : A mixture of **9a** (0.01 mol), appropriate amine (0.01 mol) and absolute ethanol (30 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The solid obtained was crystallized from proper solvent : **10** (ethanol) (85%), m.p. 195° (Found : C, 70.20; H, 5.70; N, 9.10). C₂₆H₂₄N₃O₂Cl requires : C, 70.03; H, 5.38; N, 9.42%, ν_{\max} 3180 (NH), 2950 (CH-aliph), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O), δ 0.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.04 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.1 (2H, d, CH₂), 2.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 4.73 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 5.00 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.92 (1H, s, NH, cancelled with D₂O), 7.3 (9H, m, ArH), 8.31 (1H, s, pyrimidine-H); **10b** (ethanol) (85%), m.p. 130° (Found : C, 67.20; H, 6.30; N, 10.40). C₂₃H₂₆N₃O₂Cl requires : C, 67.07; H, 6.31; N, 10.30%, ν_{\max} 3210 (NH), 2985 (CH-aliph), 1665 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

3-Amino-4-imino-8,8-dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-8H-6-oxo-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidien (11) : A suspension of **9a** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was stirred at room temperature for 1 h. The solid formed was crystallized from benzene, (80%), m.p. 228° (Found : C, 61.20; H, 5.40; N, 15.30). C₁₉H₁₉N₄O₂Cl requires : C, 61.53; H, 5.12; N, 15.11%, ν_{\max} 3325, 3303, 3215 (NH, NH₂), 2956 (CH-aliph), 1681 cm⁻¹ (C=O), *m/z* 371 (32.36%), 372

(17.71%), 373 (4.4%), 368 (100%).

9,9-Dimethyl-12-(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-11-one (12). *Method (F)* : A solution of **11** (0.01 mol) in triethyl orthoformate (10 ml) was stirred at 70° for 6 h and then cooled overnight. The obtained solid was crystallized from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 142° (Found : C, 63.20; H, 4.70; N, 14.50). C₂₀H₁₇N₄O₂Cl requires : C, 63.07; H, 4.46; N, 14.71%; ν_{\max} 3060 (CH-arom), 2960 (CH-aliph.), 1660 cm⁻¹ (C=O). *Method (F)* : A solution of **11** (0.01 mol) in formic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The obtained solid was collected to give **12** (m.p. and m.m.p.).

3-Acetamido-4-imino-8,8-dimethyl-5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3,4,5,6,7,9-hexahydro-8H-6-oxo-chromeno[2,3-d]pyrimidine (13) : A mixture of **11** (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. After cooling, the solid separated was crystallized from ethanol, (72%), m.p. 144° (Found : C, 61.30; H, 4.80; N, 13.80). C₂₁H₂₁N₄O₃Cl requires : C, 61.09; H, 5.09; N, 13.57%; ν_{\max} 3400, 3220 (NH), 2960 (CH-aliph.), 1735, 1662 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

2,9,9-Trimethyl-12-(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-11-one (14) : A mixture of **11** (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. After cooling, the solid separated was crystallized from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 265° (Found : C, 63.70; H, 5.00; N, 14.50). C₂₁H₁₉N₄O₂Cl requires : C, 63.87; H, 4.81; N, 14.91%; ν_{\max} 3050 (CH-arom.), 2995 (CH-aliph.), 1654 cm⁻¹ (C=O), δ 1.01 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.10 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.16 (2H, d, CH₂), 2.3 (2H, d, CH₂), 2.39 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.29 (1H, s, 4H-pyran), 7.3 (4H, AB-system), 9.51 (1H, s, pyrimidine-H), *m/z* 395 (27.79%), 396 (32.42%), 234 (100%).

9,9-Ddimethyl-2,12-bis(4-chlorophenyl)-8,10,11,12-tetrahydro-9H-chromeno[3,2-e][1,2,4]triazolo[1,5-c]pyrimidin-11-one (15). *Method (G)* : A mixture of **11** (0.01 mol), *p*-chlorobenzoyl chloride (or *p*-chloro-benzaldehyde, (0.01 mol) and pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed for 10 h. The reaction mixture was evaporated, the residue triturated with ethanol and the solid formed was crystallized from ethanol, (65%), m.p. 255° (Found : C, 63.30; H, 4.20; N, 11.60). C₂₆H₂₀N₄O₂Cl₂ requires : C, 63.67; H, 4.08; N, 11.42%; ν_{\max} 2950 (CH-aliph), 1681 cm⁻¹ (C=O). *Method (H)* : A mixture of **11** (0.01 mol), *p*-chlorobenzaldehyde (0.01 mol), dioxane (15 ml) and catalytic amount of piperidine was refluxed for 16 h and the solid formed after cooling was crystallized to yield **15** (m.p. and m.m.p.).

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